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Cleaning strategies for 3D-printed porous scaffolds used for bone regeneration fabricated via ceramic vat photopolymerization

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ABSTRACT

Vat photopolymerization has gained prominence in bone tissue engineering owing to its capability to fabricate intricate structures that closely mimic the natural bone tissue. Thorough cleaning of uncured ceramic slurry from the as-printed structures is essential, as the presence of residue within the structure can obstruct pores during sintering. Given the limitations of conventional spray cleaning for these structures, this study seeks to investigate alternative cleaning approaches. Specifically, the efficacy of dibasic ester (DBE) and LithaSol 80, coupled with ultrasonic and soaking methods, is examined to identify optimal strategies for the thorough removal of viscous residual slurry (LithaBone HA 480). To examine the effect of temperature on cleaning ability, printed scaffolds were soaked in the cleaning solutions at 23, 30, 40, and 50 °C for 24 h. Based on the results, 50 °C was chosen as the temperature for further analysis while using both soaking (24, 48, 72 and 96 h) and ultrasonic (5, 15 and 30 min; 1, 2, 3, and 4 h) as the cleaning methods. The cross-sectional image of the scaffolds showed that at least 48 h and 30 min is required for effective cleaning with soaking and ultrasonic, respectively. Microstructure analysis of scaffolds cleaned with LithaSol 80 revealed smoother surfaces, while scaffolds treated with DBE showed visibly contracted pores with peeling effect suggesting that DBE exerts a more aggressive action on the cured slurry in contrast to LithaSol 80. Notably, significant difference in mass loss was observed between scaffolds treated with LithaSol 80 and DBE. The significantly higher mass loss observed with DBE suggests that it not only impacts uncured slurry but also possibly affects cured slurry. Accordingly, the results indicate that DBE is notably more effective in cleaning; however, LithaSol 80 is more appropriate for maintaining structural integrity combined with soaking cleaning method. No significant difference was observed in compressive strength between most sintered scaffolds.

1. Introduction

Each year, an estimated \$45 billion is allocated for treating nearly 15 million patients affected by bone-related disorders, which include trauma-related fractures and osteoporotic bone defects. Specifically in the United States, approximately 1.6 million patients undergo bone grafting procedures annually, amounting to a cost of roughly \$2.5 billion [1]. The use of cutting-edge additive manufacturing (AM) technology in bone tissue engineering (BTE) has been a growing trend in recent years, allowing for the fabrication of intricate structures that closely resemble bone tissue with personalized shapes. This innovative approach utilizes biomaterials to construct bone scaffolds featuring a

three-dimensional porous design. The process involves integrating cells and growth factors into the scaffold, and eventually implanting the customized scaffold into the targeted bone defect site [2,3].

Among various AM technologies used in BTE, ceramic vat photopolymerization (VPP) has gained increasing attention due to its capabilities to fabricate bone scaffolds featuring a variety of intricate porous patterns that were traditionally challenging to manufacture for bone regeneration. In the ceramic VPP process using digital light projection (DLP), a lateral resolution of approximately 40 μm can be achieved [4, 5]. This makes it an ideal manufacturing method for producing the predominant pore structure found in bone scaffolds, namely the orthogonal periodic arrangement. This porous configuration showcases

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Fig. 1. A cross-sectional view of the CAD model utilized in preliminary studies alongside the micro-CT image displaying the sintered scaffold cleaned using pressurized air and LithaSol 80.

Fig. 2. Side- and top-view orientations of the scaffold CAD model generated through nTopology software.

Table 1
Preconditioning, debinding and sintering programs used after cleaning process.

	heating rate (K/ min)	temperature (°C)	dwelt time (h)
Preconditioning	0.20	75	3
	0.20	90	5
	0.20	110	12
	0.20	120	38
	-0.25	30	0
Debinding and Sintering	0.20	160	10.5
	0.20	180	7
	0.20	220	7
	0.20	300	7
	0.20	325	6
	0.20	430	6
	0.20	500	0
	1.70	900	2
	0.50	1100	2
	-2.00	900	2
-4.00	30		

a consistent distribution of pores, meeting essential criteria for substance exchange and bone tissue growth [2]. While ceramic VPP exhibits no limitations in producing these intricate structures, characterized by small, interconnected pores and channels, cleaning such as-printed porous structures poses a significant challenge due to the inherent characteristics of the ceramic VPP process [6]. In ceramic VPP, a light source selectively solidifies specific regions based on the computer-aided design (CAD) file, leading to the formation of cured layers; a more detailed description of the technique can be found

elsewhere [4]. The challenge of cleaning arises in the creation of porous structures where the interconnected pores are intentionally designed to remain uncured. The uncured slurry in these porous regions can become intricately trapped between the cured layers, complicating the cleaning process. Effectively removing the uncured slurry from within the intricate and porous geometries of the printed structures becomes a critical task as the presence of residue within the structure can obstruct pores during sintering. This is particularly important in applications such as biomedical implants where pore characteristics are crucial for tissue integration and substance exchange. Therefore, such structures demand specialized effective cleaning methodologies to ensure the structural integrity and functionality of the final components [6–9].

Numerous cleaning solutions have been selected in different studies to clean as-printed structures, e.g. isopropanol [10–12], dibasic ester [3, 13], diphenylether [14], LithaSol 20 [15], LithaSol 30 [16], while Schwarzer et al. [7] examined effect of three different solvents (glycerine, ethylene glycol and ethanol) on the as-printed macroporous structures. The quality of the final component was directly influenced by the cleaning method, cleaning time, and the cleaning agent used. Ethanol, despite its superior cleaning capability, failed to produce defect-free components. Ultrasonic cleaning in combination with ethanol caused deformation of the printed green parts. Ethylene glycol and glycerine yielded inferior cleaning results compared to ethanol, but defects were present in all trials. The properties of ethanol, such as low viscosity and excellent solubility in nonpolar phases, contributed to its effective cleaning but also increased the risk of diffusion into the built part, leading to swelling, internal stresses, and potential cracks. Physical cleaning with a cotton swab impregnated with the agent, followed by compressed air spraying, proved most effective in removing suspension [7]. Further, in study by Johansson et al. [17] acetone showed good cleaning ability, but caused swelling and delamination, whereas 1-octanol and PEG-200 both showed poor cleaning ability with no delamination. Ethanol showed both poor cleaning ability and caused delamination, and iso-propanol moderate cleaning ability with moderate delamination, while a mixture of dibasic esters showed both excellent cleaning ability and minimal delamination formation. Another study [6] addressed the cleaning challenges related to small holes, in which a new cleaning strategy was introduced for the design of cleaning agents on the basis of competitive absorption of viscosity-reducing dispersants on the surface of ceramic particles within viscoelastic pastes. By combining these agents with specific cleaning equipment, the paste flow was enhanced during ultrasonic cleaning and spraying. Ultrasonic cleaning was better for small holes but caused more structural damage, while spray cleaning resulted in lower surface roughness, less damage, and reduced residual paste [6]. The literature highlights that various cleaning solutions exhibit differing cleaning efficiencies. This variation is attributed to the specific composition of the monomer component in the ceramic slurry. The effectiveness of a cleaning solution, whether it is good, moderate, or poor, depends on how well cleaning solution acts as a solvent for the monomer in the ceramic slurry.

However, spray cleaning is not appropriate for complex shaped structures that mimic natural bone porosity due to inaccessibility of the interconnected pores. Our preliminary study proved the inefficiency of spray cleaning of as-printed biomimetic scaffold. Fig. 1 presents the CAD model used in this study alongside the micro-CT image captured scaffold post-spray cleaned with LithaSol 80 solution and sintering at 1300 °C. The micro-CT visualization reveals a fully dense inner scaffold, highlighting the ineffectiveness of spray cleaning for scaffolds of this specific design. To the best of the authors' knowledge, no systematic research has been published on cleaning bone biomimetic scaffolds or other highly complex structures with small, interconnected pores obtained by ceramic VPP. In addition to the lack of systematic studies, only a limited number of studies have investigated the effects of cleaning methods on structures printed using ceramic VPP.

To fill this gap, this study aims to identify suitable cleaning strategies that effectively remove residual slurry from intricate structures with

Fig. 3. The illustration of the characterization protocol. Created with [BioRender.com](https://www.biorender.com).

Fig. 4. (a) Control sample image and SEM micrographs. Scale bar: 1 mm, 200 μm and 20 μm . (b) Viscosity of LithaBone HA 480 slurry as a function of shear rate at 23, 30, 40, 50 and 60 °C (c) Cross-sectional images of scaffolds after soaking for 24 h in LithaSol 80 and DBE at 23, 30, 40, and 50 °C. (d) Cross-sectional images of scaffolds following ultrasonic treatment for 5 and 15 min in LithaSol 80 and DBE at 50 °C.

hard-to-reach areas without damaging the microstructure. Accordingly, soaking and ultrasonic cleaning methods combined with various cleaning solutions were examined to address which strategy is more

suitable for cleaning complex structures obtained from high viscosity slurry. This study systematically investigates the influence of cleaning solutions, as well as the temperature and duration of cleaning treatments

Fig. 5. Images of side and cross-section view of scaffolds soaked in LithaSol 80 and DBE after soaking for 48, 72 and 96 h. (b) SEM micrographs of scaffolds. Defects on the scaffolds surface are depicted in red arrows. Scale bar: 1 mm, 200 and 20 μm . (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

on surface morphology, thermogravimetric behavior, and mechanical properties. It provides valuable insights into how different cleaning strategies affect the properties of the as-printed and sintered structures. Anticipating the growing complexity and smaller-scale requirements for printed structures in ceramic VPP, the authors assert that this research holds significant potential in facilitating effective cleaning procedures without compromising the ultimate properties of the fabricated components.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Design of the CAD model and ceramic VPP printing

The CAD model (Fig. 2), featuring a cylindrical shape with dimensions of 10.5×8.5 mm (height \times diameter), was designed using nTopology 3.35.2 software and exported as an .stl-file. The design parameters in nTopology software were set as follows: point spacing of 0.7 mm, random seed of 20, thickness of 0.12 mm, tolerance of 0.13 mm, and rounded edges. LithaBone HA 480 (Lithoz GmbH), a commercial hydroxyapatite slurry, was used for the printing of scaffolds. The printing was done using a CeraFab 7500 printer (Lithoz GmbH), while

Fig. 6. (a) Scaffolds difference in dimensions before and after cleaning treatment. The significant difference between the two groups (*): $p < 0.05$. (b) TG analysis of scaffolds after soaking treatment. The initial mass loss for DBE-treated and LithaSol 80-treated samples is indicated by black and red arrows, respectively. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

the interlayer thickness, light intensity and curing time were set to 25 μm , 65 mW/cm^2 and 1.384 s, respectively.

2.2. Selection of cleaning methods and cleaning solutions

As spray cleaning is unsuitable for highly complex structures, soaking and ultrasonic methods were selected for cleaning. An ultrasonic bath with temperature control (M30, FinnSonic Oy, Finland) at an ultrasonic frequency of 40 kHz was used for ultrasonic cleaning. Preliminary studies investigated the cleaning effectiveness of various solutions, including isopropanol (Sigma Aldrich), dibasic ester (DBE, Sigma Aldrich), and two commercial cleaning solutions for printed structures via ceramic VPP: LithaSol 30 and LithaSol 80 both supplied by Lithoz GmbH. The selected commercial and non-commercial cleaning solutions were chosen based on their prevalent usage in the literature, while LithaSol 80 is new cleaning solution on market with no previously reported cleaning ability and effect on green body. The as-printed scaffolds were immersed in each solution at room temperature. After 24 h, the cleaning effectiveness was assessed by observing the cleaning capability of both the outer and inner parts of the scaffolds. The cross-sectional image of the scaffolds treated with isopropanol and LithaSol 30 can be found in Supplementary materials (Fig. S1). It can be observed that both of these cleaning solutions failed to effectively clean the as-

printed structures and were therefore excluded from further analysis. Ultimately, two cleaning solutions with the highest efficacy for cleaning the as-printed scaffolds were identified for further studies: LithaSol 80 and DBE.

2.3. Design of the experiments

To assess the effect of temperature on cleaning efficacy, first the rheological behavior of hydroxyapatite based ceramic VPP slurry LithaBone HA 480 was studied at five different temperatures (25, 30, 40, 50, and 60 °C) using a stress-controlled rotational rheometer (Physica MCR-301, Anton Paar GmbH, Austria). The rotational rheometer used a concentric cylinder system (DIN EN ISO 3219 and DIN 53019), equipped with a cup and a stirring rod. The gap between the cup and the stirring rod was set to 1 mm. The rheological behaviour was examined by subjecting the slurry to shear rates within the range of 1–1000 s^{-1} . Followed by viscosity measurements, a soaking test was conducted on the as-printed scaffolds to assess the effect of temperature on cleaning effectiveness of the cleaning solutions. Accordingly, the as-printed scaffolds were immersed in the cleaning solutions at 23, 30, 40, and 50 °C, over 24 h. The scaffolds were then cleaned using an airbrush, followed by cutting with a blade to image the cross section using a digital camera.

Once an optimized temperature was selected based on the achieved results, the as-printed scaffolds were immersed in the chosen cleaning solutions (LithaSol 80 and DBE) within black containers to prevent post-photopolymerization from daylight exposure. The containers were positioned in a heating cabinet and an ultrasonic bath for soaking and ultrasonic cleaning, respectively, both set at 50 °C.

To assess the impact of treatment duration on cleaning efficacy, various time points were selected. For cleaning by soaking the selected time points were 48, 72 and 96 h. Accordingly, the scaffolds treated in LithaSol 80 were labelled as LS80_S_48h, LS80_S_72h, LS80_S_96h, while those treated in DBE were labelled as DBE_S_48h, DBE_S_72h, DBE_S_96h. For ultrasonic cleaning, the selected points were 5, 15, 30 min and 1, 2, 3 and 4 h. The corresponding labels are LS80_U_5min, LS80_U_15min, LS80_U_30min, LS80_U_1h, LS80_U_2h, LS80_U_3h, LS80_U_4h for LithaSol 80, and DBE_U_5min, DBE_U_15min, DBE_U_30min, DBE_U_1h, DBE_U_2h, DBE_U_3h, DBE_U_4h for DBE treatment. After cleaning, scaffolds were cleaned with airbrush to remove residual cleaning solution.

2.4. Heat treatments

After cleaning, the preconditioning, debinding and sintering processes were conducted with a heat treatment profile outlined in Table 1, using a laboratory-scale muffle furnace (RHF1500, Carbolite, UK).

2.5. Characterizing the scaffolds

To assess the impact of the cleaning solution on scaffold dimensions, measurements were taken using an external micrometer both before and after the cleaning process, as well as after sintering. The microstructure of the scaffolds was analyzed using a scanning electron microscope (SEM, JSM-IT500LA, Jeol, Japan) at an accelerating voltage of 15 kV, after both the cleaning and sintering processes. An as-printed and non-treated scaffold was used as a control sample. To obtain SEM images of the control, the scaffold was cut into smaller pieces to facilitate removal of the uncured slurry. The green bodies of the scaffolds demonstrated structural stability while remaining sufficiently soft to be easily sectioned using a surgical blade. Pressurized air and a small amount of LithaSol 80 were used to remove any uncured slurry. Prior to imaging, scaffolds were coated with gold for 180 s, using a sputter coater (S150 Sputter Coater, Edwards). In addition to SEM imaging, the cleaned scaffolds were imaged by a digital camera in micro mode.

The cleaned scaffolds were subjected to thermogravimetric (TG) analysis using a Netzsch thermo-microbalance analyzer (TG 209 F3

Fig. 7. Cleaning mechanisms with (a) LithaSol80 and (b) DBE.

Tarsus, Netzsch, Germany). The analysis involved heating samples in an aluminum oxide crucible from 40 °C to 600 °C at a heating rate of 10 °C/min. The measurements were conducted in a controlled environment using a combination of synthetic air (20 ml/min) and nitrogen gas (80 ml/min).

After sintering, the obtained cylindrical scaffolds ($n = 5$, where n is the number of measured samples) underwent compression testing using the non-hydraulic Instron 5960 testing machine (Instron Ltd., United States) at a strain rate of 0.5 mm/min at room temperature ($T = 23.0 \text{ °C} \pm 0.5$). Throughout the test, compressive load and displacement were continuously recorded at 0.1 s intervals using a 2 kN load cell. The software linked to the testing machine was utilized to determine the maximum compressive engineering stress using the entire sample diameter. The stress (σ) was computed by dividing the applied force (F) by the cross-sectional area (A) of the scaffolds. Additionally, the strain (ϵ) was calculated as the change in height (Δh) divided by the initial scaffold height (h_0) corresponding to engineering strain. The illustration of the characterization protocol is depicted in Fig. 3.

2.6. Statistical analysis

Quantitative results were presented as mean \pm standard deviation. Statistical analysis was conducted using a one-way analysis, with statistical significance denoted by $p < 0.05$ (*) when differences were observed.

3. Results and discussion

The unique properties of viscoelastic materials pose challenges in removing excess slurry from printed structures [6]. Despite its high viscosity of 24 Pa s, the slurry used in this study was effectively distributed within the vat, allowing for successful fabrication. However, the high viscosity of the slurry presented challenges during the cleaning process of printed complex scaffolds. Hence, investigating the influence

of temperature on enhancing slurry flowability and its consequential impact on the cleaning process stands as a crucial parameter requiring examination for successful cleaning.

3.1. Characterization of the control sample

As shown in Fig. 4a, unpolymerized slurry is discernible within the inner section of the scaffold (control), signifying that traditional cleaning methods involving pressurized air and solvent are ineffective for cleaning intricate structures of this nature, resulting in pore blockage, as shown in Fig. 1. The SEM micrographs, presented in Fig. 4a, revealed a smooth surface absent of any visible cracks or irregularities.

3.2. The effect of temperature on viscosity and cleaning efficiency

Increasing the temperature is effective in lowering viscosity and improving slurry flowability, leading to enhanced cleaning of the as-printed structures. Given the high viscosity of the slurry and the intricate nature of the printed structure, an examination of slurry viscosity at varying temperatures was conducted to identify the optimal cleaning temperature as the initial parameter in this study. Fig. 4b shows the viscosity of the slurry vs. shear rate at the temperature of 23, 30, 40, 50, and 60 °C. At temperatures of 23 and 30 °C, a peak in viscosity is observed at low shear rates. Before reaching this peak, the slurry undergoes elastic deformation, and after the peak, it begins to flow. This behavior is not seen at 40, 50, and 60 °C. However, at all temperatures, viscosity decreases with increasing shear rate. The viscosity is higher at 23 and 30 °C, displaying stronger viscoelastic behavior and more pronounced shear thinning. Notably, at 40, 50, and 60 °C, viscosity decreases sharply within a small shear rate range before stabilizing. Lower viscosity at higher temperatures is attributed to the fact that an elevated temperature increases the kinetic energy of the resin molecules [18]. Further, the shear thinning effect suggests that the slurries can be classified as non-Newtonian fluids, exhibiting typical rheological behavior

Fig. 8. (a) Images of side and cross-section view of scaffolds ultrasonically treated in LithaSol 80 for 30 min, 1, 2, 3 and 4 h. (b) SEM micrographs of scaffolds. Defects on the scaffolds surface are depicted in red arrows. Scale bar: 1 mm, 200 and 20 μm . (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

characteristic of other ceramic slurries [19]. Specifically, at a shear rate of 200 s^{-1} , the viscosity was recorded as 20.32 Pa s at 23 °C, 13.15 Pa s at 30 °C, 6.64 Pa s at 40 °C, 3.00 Pa s at 50 °C, and 1.45 Pa s at 60 °C. By increasing temperature, the viscosity of the slurry significantly decreases and becomes flowable which can then lead to better cleaning performance of the complex scaffolds. Notably, the difference in viscosity of slurry at 50 and 60 °C was small, leading to the exclusion of 60 °C from further studies to mitigate any risk of thermal polymerization of the ceramic slurry during the cleaning process.

To further examine the effect of temperature on the cleaning ability, printed scaffolds were soaked in the cleaning solutions (LithaSol 80 or DBE) at 23, 30, 40, and 50 °C for 24 h. As can be seen in Fig. 4c, LithaSol 80 failed to achieve complete cleaning at any temperature within the specified timeframe, whereas DBE exhibited inadequate cleaning performance at 23 °C but demonstrated effectiveness at other temperatures in achieving thorough scaffold cleaning. Therefore, it can be concluded that increasing temperature during cleaning provides an effective method to enhance the flowability of the uncured slurry from the pores of the as-printed scaffolds. Based on these findings, 50 °C was chosen as the temperature for further analysis for both soaking and ultrasonic

cleaning.

Given that the scaffolds were not fully cleaned within 24 h using LithaSol 80, soaking experiments were extended to 48, 72, and 96 h. For ultrasonic cleaning, preliminary experiments using 5 and 15-min intervals with both LithaSol 80 and DBE did not yield satisfactory results (Fig. 4d). Consequently, time intervals of 30 min, 1, 2, 3, and 4 h were selected for ultrasonic cleaning. Although 48 h of soaking or 30 min of ultrasonic cleaning are sufficient to fully remove uncured resin, longer cleaning periods were tested to evaluate their impact on scaffold properties. In real-life scenarios, patients with larger bone defects would require bigger scaffolds, which in turn would necessitate extended cleaning times.

3.3. Effect of soaking treatment on as-printed structures

3.3.1. Morphological characterizations

Fig. 5a shows side and cross-section views of scaffolds after immersion in LithaSol 80 and DBE solutions for durations of 48, 72, and 96 h, while Fig. 5b displays SEM micrographs of the scaffolds. All scaffolds showed fully cleaned structures without unpolymerized slurry within

Fig. 9. (a) Images of side and cross-section view of scaffolds ultrasonically treated in DBE for 48, 72 and 96 h. (b) SEM micrographs of scaffolds. Defects on the scaffolds surface are depicted in red arrows. Scale bar: 1 mm, 200 and 20 μm . (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

the pores. The SEM analysis of scaffolds cleaned with LithaSol 80 revealed smoother surfaces in comparison to the micrograph of the control sample (Fig. 4a). However, in scaffold LS80_96h, a few visible cracks were observed indicated a weakened structure, likely resulting from a prolonged cleaning treatment. SEM imaging of the scaffold soaked in DBE showed visibly contracted pores compared to those treated with LithaSol 80. Moreover, closer examination at higher magnifications revealed a peeling effect on the surface that can be attributed to the potential corrosive effects of DBE on the materials involved.

3.3.2. Scaffolds dimensions and thermogravimetric analysis

Fig. 6a shows the dimensions of the as-printed scaffolds after cleaning. A similar pattern of decrease of height and diameter was observed between the scaffolds treated with DBE and LithaSol 80. However, the statistical analysis confirmed a noticeable reduction in the height of the scaffolds after 72 and 96 h soaked in LithaSol 80, compared to scaffolds soaked for 48 h. Similarly, a significant decrease in diameter was noted after 96 h of soaking in LithaSol 80 compared to scaffolds soaked for 48 h.

Fig. 6b illustrates the thermal degradation characteristics observed

during thermogravimetric (TG) analysis of the as-printed scaffolds. Notably, a significant difference in mass loss was observed between scaffolds treated with LithaSol 80 and DBE. Scaffolds treated with LithaSol 80 exhibited mass losses of 32.04 % for LS80_S_48h, 32.64 % for LS80_S_72h, and 33.56 % for LS80_S_96h. In contrast, scaffolds treated with DBE displayed mass losses of 18.17 % for DBE_S_48h, 18.57 % for DBE_S_72h, and 19.05 % for DBE_S_96h. The significantly lower mass loss observed in DBE suggests that it not only impacts uncured slurry but possibly affects cured slurry. The TG analysis indicated that mass loss started at approximately 150 $^{\circ}\text{C}$, primarily attributed to the diffusion and evaporation of additives, unreactive diluents and uncured slurry. The degradation of the major cured organic components initiated around 250 $^{\circ}\text{C}$. The significant contrast in the TG curves between scaffolds treated with LithaSol 80 and DBE primarily lies in the initial stage of weight loss. Scaffolds treated with LithaSol 80 experienced a weight loss of approximately 20.56 %, while those treated with DBE showed a loss of around 5.18 % at around 250 $^{\circ}\text{C}$. This suggests that DBE has been notably more effective in facilitating the removal of additives, diluents, and uncured slurry from the as-printed structures during the cleaning treatments. These results emphasize the superior cleaning efficacy of

Fig. 10. (a) Scaffolds difference in dimensions before and after cleaning treatment. The significant difference between the two groups (*): $p < 0.05$. (b) TG analysis of scaffolds after ultrasonic treatment. The initial mass loss for DBE-treated and LithaSol 80-treated samples is indicated by black and red arrows, respectively. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

DBE compared to LithaSol 80. However, while DBE can be characterized as a more effective cleaning solution, it is more aggressive towards the surface of the analyzed slurry, resulting in visible damage in the form of surface defects (Fig. 5b). The observed difference in total mass loss (around 14.15 %) between samples treated with LithaSol 80 and DBE implies the potential occurrence of chemical debinding during cleaning with DBE. Based on the TG analysis, shrinkage would be expected in the samples treated with DBE. However, the experimental data showed the opposite result. Possible cleaning mechanisms using LithaSol 80 and DBE are presented in Fig. 7. However, further detailed examination is required to provide conclusive evidence and explain shrinkage opposite to expected according to TG analysis.

3.4. Effect of ultrasonic treatment on as-printed structures

3.4.1. Morphological characterizations

Fig. 8a exhibits side and cross-section views of scaffolds following ultrasonic treatment in LithaSol 80 for durations of 30 min, 1, 2, 3, and 4 h, while Fig. 8b shows SEM micrographs of these scaffolds. All specimens demonstrated completely cleaned scaffolds without residual unpolymerized slurry within the pores. SEM analysis of scaffolds treated for 30 min and 1 h displayed smooth surfaces, as observed in the micrograph of the control sample (Fig. 4a). However, in scaffolds LS80_U_2h, LS80_U_3h, and LS80_U_4h, visible defects, such as circular

defects and cracks, were observed. These findings suggest that prolonged ultrasonic treatment leads to surface damage due to the mechanical stress generated by high-frequency vibrations and the liquid cavitation effect.

Fig. 9a presents side and cross-section views of scaffolds after ultrasonic treatment in DBE for durations of 30 min, 1, 2, 3, and 4 h, while Fig. 9b shows corresponding SEM micrographs. All samples exhibited thoroughly cleaned scaffolds without residual unpolymerized slurry within the pores. Upon SEM analysis, scaffolds treated for 30 min and 1 h displayed surface damage characterized by a peeling effect. However, with longer ultrasonic treatment in scaffolds DBE_U_2h, DBE_U_3h, and DBE_U_4h, no peeling effect was observed; instead, visible defects similar to those seen in scaffolds LS80_U_2h, LS80_U_3h, and LS80_U_4h were present. It is noteworthy that, upon extended ultrasonic exposure, the already peeled layers may detach, contributing to the absence of a discernible peeling effect. The presence of more defects on the surface of scaffolds when treated with DBE corresponds with the effects observed during the soaking treatment.

3.4.2. Scaffolds dimensions and thermogravimetric analysis

Fig. 10a shows the dimensions of as-printed scaffold after ultrasonic cleaning. Scaffolds treated with LithaSol 80 or DBE maintained consistent dimensions regardless of the duration of ultrasonic cleaning. However, those treated with DBE exhibited a significant decrease in their dimensions compared to scaffolds treated with LithaSol 80.

Fig. 10b shows the thermal degradation behavior of the as-printed scaffolds observed during TG analysis. Similar to the soaking treatment, the analysis revealed that mass loss occurred at approximately similar temperatures. Notably, a significant difference in mass loss was evident between scaffolds treated with LithaSol 80 and DBE. Scaffolds treated with LithaSol 80 exhibited mass losses of 29.23 % for LS80_U_30min, 30.31 % for LS80_U_1h, 30.42 % for LS80_U_2h, 30.85 % for LS80_U_3h, and 33.88 % for LS80_U_4h. In contrast, scaffolds treated with DBE displayed mass losses of 23.97 % for DBE_U_30min, 21.65 % for DBE_U_1h, 22.41 % for DBE_U_2h, 22.19 % for DBE_U_3h, and 22.41 % for DBE_U_4h. The approximate 8.42 % difference in mass loss observed between samples treated with LithaSol 80 and DBE is lower than the difference observed when soaking was used as the cleaning treatment. This suggests that the duration during which scaffolds are in contact with the cleaning solution is critical in affecting the cured slurry. Similarly, in line with the soaking treatment, a notable difference is observed in the initial stage of weight loss. For instance, the average weight loss for ultrasonic treatment in DBE is lower (7.72 %) than that in LithaSol 80 (17.27 %) at 2 h cleaning duration. This again indicates possible chemical debinding of cured slurry during cleaning with DBE compared to LithaSol 80.

3.5. Effect of soaking and ultrasonic treatments on final sintered structures

3.5.1. Morphological characterizations

In Fig. 11, SEM micrographs illustrate sintered scaffolds cleaned using the soaking treatment. Scaffolds treated with LithaSol 80 generally exhibited undamaged surfaces, except for scaffold LS80_S_96h, where some cracks were observed. Conversely, those treated with DBE displayed heavily damaged surfaces with visible peeling effects. Notably, the pronounced peeling effect was more evident after sintering compared to the initial observation after the cleaning treatment. This indicates that while the peeling effect was not initially observed at this level after the cleaning treatment, the surface layers were affected by DBE, resulting in substantial peeling following debinding and sintering.

In Fig. 12, SEM micrographs depict sintered scaffolds cleaned using the ultrasonic treatment. Comparable to soaking treatment, scaffolds treated with LithaSol 80 exhibited smoother surfaces with no significant damage, except for some observed in scaffold LS80_U_1h. Similarly, scaffold DBE_U_30min displayed an undamaged surface, while scaffolds

Fig. 11. SEM micrographs of scaffolds after sintering cleaned by soaking treatment in (a) LithaSol 80 and (b) DBE. Defects on the scaffolds surface are depicted in red arrows. Scale bar: 1 mm and 200 μm . (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

DBE_U_1h, DBE_U_2h, and DBE_U_3h exhibited damaged surfaces with a peeling effect. Contrary to expectations, scaffold DBE_U_4h showed surfaces without defects. While DBE demonstrated superior cleaning capacity compared to the LithaSol 80 solution, the highly defective surface of scaffolds treated with DBE renders it unsuitable for cleaning structures where surface quality is of high importance. The peeling effect observed may be attributed to DBE diffusion into the built part, a correlation supported by the results of TG analysis. The diffusion of the cleaning solution into the polymer network, non-reactive diluent, and/or remnants of uncured binder can lead to swelling of the entire as-printed part and cause dissolution of certain slurry components. Localized swelling of the organic phases may induce internal stresses, resulting in detachment and the formation of cracks [8]. The study conducted by Martins et al. [20] involved the printing of a customized bone scaffold based on hydroxyapatite through ceramic VPP, utilizing the commercial resin (Genesis Development Resin Base) from Tethon3D. The cleaning process involved three different solvents: DBE, ethanol, and isopropanol. Microscopic images revealed topographic imperfections when structures were cleaned with DBE and ethanol. In contrast, isopropanol exhibited the best cleaning ability without causing any damage to the structure [20]. The defects caused by DBE are consistent with the findings of the present study, while the defects resulting from the use of ethanol align with the study conducted by Schwarzer et al. [8]. However, preliminary experiments in this study revealed that isopropanol was not a suitable cleaning solution for the used slurry, as it acted as a non-solvent for the slurry components. The difference between this observation and the one obtained in the study by Martins et al. [20] suggests that the choice of the cleaning solution is highly correlated with the components of the used slurries. Libermann et al. [21] investigated the impact of post-printing cleaning methods on the geometry, transmission, roughness parameters, and flexural strength of zirconia disc-shaped structures. They used LithaCon 3Y 210 commercial slurry and LithaSol 30 commercial cleaning solution. The study noted that longer ultrasonic pulses were detrimental to printed structures [21]. Therefore, along ensuring the appropriate cleaning solution for a

specific slurry, it is crucial to also choose the right cleaning method.

The peeling effect observed after cleaning and sintering, predominantly on the scaffold surface treated with DBE, is explained by the proposed mechanism shown in Fig. 13. TG analysis results indicate that DBE affects not only the uncured resin but also acts as a chemical debinder, impacting cured green body and its components. Since the peeling effect is confirmed at the surface without delamination of the printed layers, it is assumed that DBE strongly affects the scaffold's surface layer compared to the rest of the scaffold, weakening the layer and resulting in peeling. Due to a strong effect of DBE on surface, the material properties of the entire scaffold and surface could differ, causing varying shrinkage during sintering and exacerbating the peeling effect at the peeling point beyond what is observed in the green body.

3.5.2. Scaffolds dimensions and mechanical properties

Scaffolds dimensions after sintering showed similar values without significant difference between them for groups treated by soaking (Fig. 14a) and ultrasonic (Fig. 14b) cleaning method. As a difference in scaffolds dimensions were observed before sintering, especially for scaffolds treated in DBE by ultrasonic cleaning, it can be assumed that dimensions were decreased due to the elimination of the slurry components leading to same dimensions of scaffolds after sintering. However, when comparing scaffolds across groups for each cleaning method, the results revealed significantly smaller dimensions in sintered scaffolds cleaned using the soaking method for both cleaning solutions. This suggests that extended soaking times may affect not only the organic component but also the ceramic material on the scaffold surface, leading to reduced dimensions. This observation is further supported by the pre-sintering measurements, where scaffolds subjected to soaking (Fig. 6a) exhibited smaller dimensions compared to those cleaned via ultrasonic treatment (Fig. 10a). After sintering, the characteristic blue colour, typical for heat-treated hydroxyapatite, was observed (Fig. 14c). The presence of small quantities of manganese in hydroxyapatite leads to a blue hue post-sintering at elevated temperatures in an oxidizing setting. This alteration is linked to the oxidation process of manganese ions

Fig. 12. SEM micrographs of scaffolds after sintering ultrasonically treated in (a) LithaSol 80 and (b) DBE. Defects on the scaffolds surface are depicted in red arrows. Scale bar: 1 mm and 200 μm . (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

within the distinctive crystal structure of hydroxyapatite [22].

The compressive strength of the porous scaffolds was evaluated using the maximum stress data presented in Fig. 14d. There was no significant difference observed in compressive strength between most scaffolds, except for significantly lower compressive strength in scaffolds DBE_S_48h and DBE_S_72h compared to scaffold DBE_U_2h. This suggests that surface defects resulting from soaking in the DBE solution led to substantial damage, consequently reducing the mechanical properties of these scaffolds. Mechanical properties of scaffolds treated with LithaSol 80 remained consistent across all treatment times and cleaning methods. In contrast, scaffolds treated with DBE exhibited a tendency toward improved mechanical properties with increasing time of treatment, even though the increase was not statistically significant. While defects caused a slight reduction in mechanical properties compared to scaffolds treated with LithaSol 80, the observed improvement in DBE-treated samples can be attributed to chemical debinding during the cleaning process. It is likely that by removing the organic component from the green body during cleaning, the debinding and sintering

processes had a more pronounced effect on the ceramic portion of the scaffold. This suggests the potential of chemical debinding to enhance mechanical properties or reduce the time required for debinding. However, further investigation and optimization are necessary to mitigate issues such as layer peeling and crack formation. The compressive strength of all scaffolds fell within the range of 3.96–6.20 MPa. Cortical bone typically displays strength varying from 1 to 100 MPa [23]. Obtained scaffolds fall in this range and are suitable to be used as bone scaffolds for cortical bone regeneration.

4. Conclusion

In present study, the effectiveness of DBE and LithaSol 80, combined with ultrasonic and soaking cleaning methods, was evaluated for removing residual LithaBone HA 480 slurry. The results highlighted role of temperature in improving cleaning efficiency, with 50 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ selected as the optimal temperature for both treatments.

The experiments showed that DBE cleaned as-printed structures

Fig. 13. Effect of the cleaning solution on the green body causing peeling effect on the surface. Created with BioRender.com.(For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

Fig. 14. Scaffolds difference in dimensions after sintering of scaffolds cleaned by (a) soaking and (b) ultrasonic treatment. The significant difference between the two groups (*): $p < 0.05$. (c) Side and top view of scaffold after sintering. (d) Compressive strength of scaffolds after sintering process.

more aggressively, causing defects like peeled layers and voids, especially during ultrasonic cleaning. However, extended ultrasonic cleaning smoothed surfaces by removing peeled layers. The TG analysis indicated possibility of chemical debinding cleaning with DBE, shown by lower mass loss below 250 °C compared to as-printed structures cleaned with LithaSol 80. Ultrasonic cleaning was more effective than soaking when DBE was used. Samples treated with DBE showed greater shrinkage compared to samples treated with LithaSol 80. Cracks appeared after 96 h of soaking, while ultrasonic cleaning caused cracks and voids after 2 h or more of treatment. Statistical analysis revealed no significant difference in compressive strength for most sintered scaffolds, except for a marked reduction in scaffolds soaked for 48 and 72 h. This suggests that soaking in the DBE solution as cleaning method introduced surface defects, causing substantial damage and subsequently compromising the mechanical properties of these scaffolds. The evidence of chemical debinding with DBE indicates future studies should explore its potential to replace or shorten the traditional debinding process that requires elevated temperatures.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Antonia Ressler: Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Resources, Project administration, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Setareh Zakeri:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Investigation, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Piie Konnunaho:** Investigation. **Martin Schwentenwein:** Writing – review & editing, Validation. **Erkki Levänen:** Writing – review & editing, Resources. **Erkka J. Frankberg:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Resources, Funding acquisition.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ceramint.2024.10.160>.

Data availability

The data that support the findings of this study are available on request from the corresponding author

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